

A Study On Consumer Perception Towards Sustainable Packaging with Reference to Tirupur

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Abstract – Sustainable packaging has become an important aspect of modern business practices due to increasing environmental concerns such as plastic pollution, waste generation, and climate change. Consumers are becoming more aware of eco-friendly products and prefer brands that use recyclable, biodegradable, and reusable packaging materials. This study aims to analyse consumer perception towards sustainable packaging and its impact on purchasing decisions. The study is based on primary data collected through a structured questionnaire. The findings reveal that consumers show a positive attitude towards sustainable packaging, but factors such as cost, convenience, and awareness influence their final purchase decisions. The study highlights the need for companies to adopt sustainable packaging to improve brand image and environmental responsibility.

Keywords – Sustainable packaging Sales Performance, Social Media Marketing, Customer Engagement, Brand Awareness, Markets, Business Growth, Marketing Strategies, Customer Reach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable packaging refers to the use of environmentally friendly materials and practices in packaging products. It includes recyclable, biodegradable, and reusable packaging solutions that reduce environmental impact. With the rapid increase in environmental issues such as plastic waste and pollution, businesses and consumers are shifting towards sustainable alternatives. Consumers today are more conscious about the environment and prefer products that minimize harm to nature. Sustainable packaging not only helps in protecting the environment but also improves brand reputation and customer loyalty. However, challenges such as high cost, lack of awareness, and limited availability affect its adoption. This study focuses on understanding consumer perception towards sustainable packaging and its influence on buying behaviour.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Magnus Hanss (2012) stated that environmental concern influences sustainable purchasing behaviour.
2. Pauline Bergelin (2009) found that consumers prefer eco-friendly packaging but are affected by price.
3. John Thogersen (1999) highlighted that positive environmental attitudes increase sustainable behaviour.
4. Koen Verghese (2015) explained that sustainable packaging reduces environmental impact.
5. Arvind Gupta (2023) concluded that sustainable packaging improves brand image and customer loyalty.

Objectives

1. To study consumer awareness towards sustainable packaging
2. To analyse the influence of sustainable packaging on purchase decisions
3. To identify factors affecting consumer preference

III. RESEARCH METHEDODOLOGY

The study is based on both primary and secondary data.

Primary Data:

Collected from 100 respondents using a structured questionnaire.

Secondary Data:

Collected from books, journals, and websites.

Sampling Method:

Convenience sampling

Tools Used:

- Percentage Analysis
- Rank Analysis

IV. DATA INTREPRETATION

AWARENESS OF SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING

S.No	Particulars	No Of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	62	62%
2	No	38	38%

Interpretation

Most respondents are aware of sustainable packaging, indicating increasing environmental awareness.

Preference For Sustainable Packaging

S.No	Particulars	No Of Respondents	Percentage
1	Always	48	48%
2	Sometimes	22	22%
3	Rarely	18	18%
4	Never	12	12%

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REFERENCE**Interpretation:**

Majority of respondents prefer sustainable packaging products.

WILLINGNESS TO PAY EXTRA

S.No	Particulars	No Of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	77	77%
2	No	23	23%

Interpretation:

Most consumers are willing to pay extra for eco-friendly packaging.

PACKAGING INFLUENCE ON PURCHASE DECISION

S.N O	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Yes	60	60%
2	No	40	40%

Interpretation:

Packaging plays a major role in influencing purchase decisions.

FINDINGS

- Majority of consumers are aware of sustainable packaging
- Consumers prefer eco-friendly packaging
- Packaging influences purchase decisions
- Most respondents are willing to pay extra
- Social media plays a major role in awareness

SUGGESTION

- * Companies should promote sustainable packaging
- * Increase consumer awareness through advertisements
- * Reduce cost of eco-friendly materials
- * Improve quality and durability of packaging
- * Government should support eco-friendly initiatives

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that sustainable packaging plays an important role in influencing consumer behaviour and brand image. Consumers are increasingly aware and supportive of eco-friendly packaging, but factors like cost and convenience still act as barriers. Companies should adopt sustainable packaging strategies to meet consumer expectations and contribute to environmental protection.